

I-adapt: Using IoU Adapter to improve pseudo labels in cross-domain object detection

Supplemental Material

1 Comparison with Harmonious Teacher

To further study the effectiveness of our I-adapt, we compare it with a recently proposed method, Harmonious Teacher (HT) [1]. This method achieves SOTA performance on CDOD tasks with relatively small domain gaps, such as Sim10k→Cityscapes. However, its performance on CDOD tasks with large domain gaps, such as PASCAL VOC→Clipart, is underexplored. Therefore, we compared it with our method on four CDOD tasks, including PASCAL VOC→Clipart, PASCAL VOC→Comic2k, Sim10k→Cityscapes, and Cityscapes→Foggy Cityscapes. The former two are with large domain gaps, and the latter two are with small domain gaps. The results are shown in Table 1, and are reported by mAP with an IoU threshold of 0.5.

Table 1: Comparison experiments in four CDOD tasks. V→CP, V→CM, S→C and C→F represent task PASCAL VOC→Clipart, PASCAL VOC→Comic2k, Sim10k→Cityscapes, Cityscapes→Foggy Cityscapes, respectively. † denotes that the results are produced using publicly released code of HT.

method	V→CP	V→CM	S→C	C→F
HT [1]	35.1 (†)	33.8 (†)	65.5	50.4
I-Adapt (ours)	51.6	45.6	57.1	46.5

Compared with HT, the performances of I-Adapt in adapting to dissimilar domains (PASCAL VOC → Clipart/Comic2k) surpass the HT by large margins of 16.5% and 11.8%. In the adaptation to more similar domains, Sim10k→Cityscapes and Cityscapes→Foggy Cityscapes, HT performs better than our I-Adapt, with margins of 8.4% and 3.9%. A possible reason is that the teacher detector of HT trained on the source domain can still perform relatively well in similar target domains, and thus generates high-quality pseudo labels. When the domain gaps are large, the qualities of generated pseudo labels degrade. In comparison, I-Adapt can generate the weights of pseudo labels and thus enable the detector to focus on learning high-quality pseudo labels. Therefore, I-Adapt achieves better performance on tasks with large domain gaps. This experiment demonstrates that I-Adapt is comparable with most recent methods.

2 More Results in Ablation study

As shown in Table 2, we conduct the ablation study on the rest of the cross-domain detection tasks. The results show that our I-Adapt works well when adapting to similar and dissimilar domains.

Table 2: More results in ablation study. CA, IA, BA, MI represent Category Adapter, IoU Adapter, Bbox Adapter, and Mutual Improvement, respectively.

(a) PASCAL VOC→Clipart.

Method	CA	IA	BA	MI	mAP(%)
Baseline	–	–	–	–	32.1
D-adapt [2]	✓	–	–	–	49.0
modules	–	✓	✓	–	48.9
	–	✓	✓	✓	51.6

(b) PASCAL VOC→Comic2k.

Method	CA	IA	BA	MI	mAP(%)
Baseline	–	–	–	–	23.8
D-adapt [2]	✓	–	–	–	40.5
modules	–	✓	✓	–	43.1
	–	✓	✓	✓	45.6

(c) Sim10k→Cityscapes.

Method	CA	IA	BA	MI	mAP(%)
Baseline	–	–	–	–	36.6
D-adapt [2]	✓	–	–	–	50.3
modules	–	✓	✓	–	55.1
	–	✓	✓	✓	57.1

Table 3: Computational cost.

Method	Training time
SWDA [4]	~18.0h
HT [1]	~14.5h
D-adapt (T=3) [2]	~16.5h
I-adapt (T=3)	~16.6h

3 Computational Cost and Parameter Quantity

Our method introduces some extra computational time during training but no extra time during inference. In particular, the proposed I-adapt is integrated with an object detector to enhance the training. After the training, I-adapt is no longer needed, and only the object detector is used during inference. Therefore, it does not introduce any computational time and parameters for inference.

We compare the training time of our method and some representative methods, including SWDA [4], HT [1], and D-adapt [2]. The results are shown in Table 3. As we can see, our method is a little slower than HT, comparable to D-adapt, and faster than SWDA.

4 Results on One-Stage Detector.

As shown in Table 4, we apply the one-stage detector RetinaNet [3] to integrate with I-adapt. I-adapt improves the detector performance

Table 4: Results from PASCAL VOC to Clipart. RetinaNet is used as the detector, and ResNet is used as the backbone.

Method	aero	bicycle	bird	boat	bottle	bus	car	cat	chair	cow	table	dog	hrs	bike	prsn	plnt	sheep	sofa	train	tv	mAP(%)
source only	25.8	37.1	27.4	17.7	27.5	54.6	33.0	18.1	35.0	23.5	22.1	11.1	28.7	44.5	37.2	33.2	4.8	25.2	38.5	40.4	29.3
D-adapt [2]	47.4	65.0	33.1	37.5	56.8	61.2	55.1	27.3	45.5	51.8	29.1	29.6	38.0	74.5	66.7	46.0	24.2	29.3	54.2	53.8	46.3
I-adapt(ours)	52.4	71.5	31.4	36.6	45.6	75.2	41.7	28.8	47.2	53.5	30.6	29.0	36.5	91.9	65.2	41.6	16.0	31.0	60.7	48.7	46.8

by 17.5% compared to the “source only” method, and surpasses D-adapt by 0.5%. The results show that I-adapt is also an effective method to adapt the one-stage detector to new domains, and has a better performance compared to D-adapt.

References

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